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Acculturation in the Portuguese overseas experience with Japan: A Rudmin Model application

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Abstract:

This paper provides a historical point of view about the acculturation phenomenon. The Portuguese historical and cultural backgrounds were employed in order to report acculturation as a reciprocal learning process, which was regulated by motivations. The current paper provides an emic point of view, because it was presumed a lack of equivalence between the Portuguese and the Anglo-Saxon cultures regarding the acculturation construct. The Portuguese minority in Japan, during the 16th century, did not prefer the integration cultural attitude regarding the Japanese majority culture. The acculturation process was antagonistic, and it was regulated by strong motivations in both cultures. However, the Portuguese minority was reporting to learn a second culture. The acculturation process was still negotiated, relative, and it was multidimensional, because the two cultures were affecting each other according to different cultural domains. Both cultures were displaying different attitudes according to their social classes.

Keywords: acculturation, Rudmin Model, fusion model, emic

Aculturação na experiência além-mar portuguesa com o Japão: Uma aplicação do modelo de Rudmin

Resumo:

Este artigo fornece um ponto de vista histórico acerca do fenómeno da aculturação. Os legados históricos e culturais portugueses foram empregues no sentido de reportarem a aculturação como um processo de aprendizagem recíproco, o qual foi regulado pelas motivações. Este artigo fornece um ponto de vista *emic*, pois foi presumido a existência duma falta de equivalência entre as culturas portuguesa e a anglo-saxónica no constructo da aculturação. A minoria portuguesa a viver no Japão, durante o século XVI, não preferiu a atitude cultural da integração face à cultura da maioria japonesa. O processo da aculturação foi antagonístico e regulado por fortes motivações em ambas as culturas. Contudo, a minoria portuguesa reportou estar a aprender uma segunda cultura. O processo da aculturação foi ainda negociado, relativo e multidimensional, uma vez que as duas culturas se influenciam mutuamente em diferentes domínios, pois ambas as culturas reportaram diferentes atitudes culturais consoante as suas classes sociais.

Palavras-chave: aculturação, modelo de Rudmin, modelo de fusão, emic

In memory of my sister Silvia Laura Peres de Castro

Introduction

Portugal started the so-called globalization process. The Portuguese cultural background is grounded on traveling and living abroad. On the Portuguese culture, the capacity to learn second cultures is a shared ideology (Almeida, 2004; Castro, 2014a). In a globalized world, all cultures are learning with each other. However, on the pervasive Berry Model (1997, 2001) the acculturation phenomenon is only approached as a matter of minority cultural attitudes. According to Berry (1997), integration means that the minority adapts the dominant second culture, keeping, however its cultural legacy untouched (see Figure number two). On the Berry Model, acculturation has just one-way of cultural transmission, and there is no mixture and cultural change. The author of the current article is Portuguese, and the Berry Model was supposing a lack of equivalence regarding his own culture. For centuries, the Portuguese culture was done by learning second cultures, and by reporting it on its own culture. The cultural adaption and its changes were reported in Brazil by Freyre (1986). However, the Brazilian case was clearly antagonistic and implied an asymmetric power relationship among cultures, races, and genders. Although, during the 16th century, in Japan, the Portuguese were a minority without military power. Moreover, for the author of the current article, Japan appeared as an example of the Portuguese cultural plasticity since his childhood; the book of F. M. Pinto was taught on his socialization. The intercultural relationships described in the book are in clear opposition regarding the pervasive Berry Model, because in the book there are interactions, reciprocal learning processes, and cultural changes. According to Freyre (1959), Fernão Mendes Pinto is the paradigm of the Portuguese capacity to get cultural adaption regarding other cultures. Opposed to the Berry Model, on the Rudmin Model (2009) acculturation is approached as a learning and motivated phenomenon. In consequence, the Rudmin Model was applied as codes on the content analysis.

On the current article, two Portuguese historical books were under analysis, and both are reporting the Portuguese relationship with Japan. The books are *The travels of Fernão Mendes*

Pinto (1974, 1989a, 1989b), and *Historia do Japam* (Fróis, 1976, 1981, 1982, 1983, 1984). Therefore, the current article offers a negative case regarding the pervasive Berry Model, and it reports the existence of a lack of equivalence between the Portuguese and the Anglo-Saxon culture. The Portuguese culture is closer to the fusion model. The content analysis outcome reports that acculturation is reciprocal, motivated, antagonistic, negotiated, multidimensional, complex, and relative. Lévi-Strauss (1998) wrote that the work of Fróis (1999a, 2001) was the best example of the proto anthropological literature, because he reported a non-Western culture with a lesser degree of ethnocentrism. Linton, in 1937, wrote about an American man who was concerned with the cultural changes in the North American culture. The American citizen did not notice that almost everything around him was done throughout the World History by many cultures. Science works by contradictions (Popper, 2002). The current article aims to report that acculturation is a two-way process of learning, and still that it is motivated. History and Anthropology (Leal, 2011) can support the current psychological literature about acculturation, in order to contextualize it. The effort to report the Westerns majorities learning should continue (Geschke, Mummendey, Kessler, & Funke, 2010; Rudmin, Villemo, & Olsen, 2007), even because it can contribute to peace and tolerance.

1. The definition of acculturation

The acculturation phenomenon is defined by its main dimensions: intercultural contact, mutual interactions among different cultures (Redfield, Linton, & Herskovits, 1936), by learning a second culture (Powell, 1880; Rudmin, 2009), and by cultural changes at individual (Graves, 1967), and at collective levels (Malinowski, 1958). In the definition of the acculturation phenomenon, it is important to take into account that the cultural changes can do reinterpretation of the own cultural legacy (Barth, 1969; Rudmin, Wang, & Castro, 2015), because acculturation is a dynamic process of cultural creation (Boas, 1982; Malinowski, 1958). It is still important to take into account that the acculturation process is regulated by strong motivations in all cultures.

2. The models to approach the acculturation phenomenon

Arends-Tóth and Van de Vijver (2006) stated that the acculturation approach has three models; assimilation, multicultural and fusion. Castro (2012, 2014a, 2015a) added the intercultural model, which is supposed to be related to the Francophone cultural background.

The main features from the acculturation models will be described. However, it is necessary to cast light in a theoretical detail. The words majority and minority are applied in the current work, because they are employed in the Anglo-Saxon context. It is necessary to standardize the concepts at the international stage, regardless that they should be targets of critical point of views. Hence, the accurate words would be dominant and dominated cultural groups.

According to Castro (2014a, 2014b), in the assimilation model, the minority culture is expected to disappear, after to be completely adapted within the majority culture. The reciprocal learning will not be reported on the expected outcome, because the minority will be assimilated within the majority culture. The European assimilation policies, during the 19th century, and the conceptualization of the Chicago School (Gordon, 1964; Park, 1928) are examples of the assimilation model.

In the multicultural model, the minority culture is expected to get cultural adaptation, maintaining, however, at the same time, its own culture (Berry, 1997). In the multicultural model, just the minority is learning, and both cultures are only interacting in the larger society. It is important to note that the larger society can not imply the segregation of the minority group, but rather a minimal interaction, which is promoted by the majority culture. The WASP culture (White, Anglo-Saxon and Protestant) is an example of the multicultural model. In the WASP culture, the fusion option was just covering the European Protestants and at least the white persons (DeTocqueville, 2002). The Berry Model (1997, 2001) is an example of the multicultural model (see Figures number two and three). On the Berry Model the minority is not changing the own cultural legacy, regardless that is learning the majority culture.

In the fusion model, there are interactions and mutual learning among different cultures, and there are still cultural mixtures (Herskovits, 1938; Simons, 1901a). Those mixtures will produce a new culture (LaFromboise, Coleman, & Gerton, 1998) with internal diversities (Bastide, 1971; Freyre, 1986; Castro, 2012, 2014a, 2004b), because the different cultures are adding new cultural features to each other. The Brazilian culture and the Freyre's theory (1986) are examples of the fusion model (Rudmin, et al., 2015; Castro, 2015a). The current paper just takes into account the main book of Freyre (1986). Thus, *The masters and the slaves*. The Luso-Tropical theory is aside, because it often takes an ambiguous meaning, which is related to asymmetric power relationships.

In the intercultural model at private and individual levels, the minority can interact and can change. However, the minority can also maintain its own cultural legacy, being applied the laissez-faire point of view at those domains. The minority at public level is expected to get cultural adaptation regarding the majority culture, for instance, at labor, and at educational domains. However, at the institutional level the interaction among different cultures is reduced. The universalistic values from the French Republic can be an example of the model, because those values are not expected to change due to the minority agency. In the light of this, the Francophone culture is an example of the model, mainly France and Quebec (Taylor, 2012).

3. The Portuguese overseas narrative regarding the acculturation topic

In the studies about the social representations of History, the Age of Discovery and the Discovery of America are among the main historical events (Cabecinhas, & Feijó, 2010; Pennebaker, Páez, & Deschamps, 2006). Portugal is supposed to have started the globalization process (Bauman, 2004; Braudel, 1943), which is characterized by global intercultural contacts, complex dependences, fast changes, and increasing cultural exchanges (Souza, 2010).

The Portuguese historical background is presumed to display a complex acculturation pattern, rather just one-way process (Lach, & Kley, 1998; Subrahmanyam, 2012). In Goa, India, the Portuguese presence caused enormous cultural shifts (Larsen, 1998). However, the

Portuguese people were also learning the local cultures. Additionally, some of the Indian cultural features were contributing to the evolution of the Western science (Lowndes, 2009; Souza, 2012). Macau, in China, is still a place where acculturation is more than a two-way process (Gunn, 2003), besides the Sino-Portuguese influence. In Japan, acculturation was also a two-way process of cultural influences.

4. Methodology

4.1 Research goals

The current paper aims to report the acculturation phenomenon as interactive and as a learning and motivated phenomenon with two-ways of cultural contributions. The pervasive Berry Model (1997, 2001) just approaches acculturation as cultural attitudes; not as interactive, motivated, and not as a learning phenomenon. The Berry Model just offers one-way of cultural contributions, because in the acculturation process is presumed that just the minority is learning the majority culture. However, the minority is expected to do not change, which is a contradiction, because the minority is learning a second culture.

4.2 Hypotheses

The work of Castro (2014a, b) applied the mixed method (Clark, & Creswell, 2011); content analysis, ethnographic work and psychometric analysis. On the current paper, just the content analysis is focused, and it can be perceived as independent. The Rudmin Model (2009) was applied as codes on the content analysis. In the current paper, the analysis outcomes are appearing together with the description of the Rudmin Model, and still with the current literature about acculturation. This paper is purposing some hypothesis:

1. In the first research hypothesis, it is supposed that the Portuguese historical narrative about acculturation does not fit in the Anglo-Saxon culture, and in the pervasive multicultural Berry Model.

2. In the second research hypothesis it is supposed that the Portuguese historical narrative is close to the fusion model and to the Gilberto Freyre (1986) theoretical rationale.

2.1. It is supposed that on the Portuguese historical narrative the motivations are ruling the cultural attitudes and that the learning process is motivated by the extrinsic motivations.

2.2. Finally, it is supposed that attitudes are different, according to the different cultural groups (Japanese and Portuguese), and according to their social classes. Therefore, there are intercultural differences, and there are also different cultural attitudes in the same cultural group.

4.3 The lack of equivalence

The current paper implies an emic approach about the acculturation phenomenon. It is presumed that there is a lack of equivalence between the Portuguese and the Anglo-Saxon cultures. The Anglo-Saxon pervasive literature is approaching acculturation as an individual attitude. However, acculturation is rooted in strong motivations, and it is placed in several cultural and historical backgrounds (Rudmin, et al., 2015).

The Portuguese historical legacy implies that the reaction towards the acculturation changes is different in comparison with the Anglo-Saxon reaction. The word integration can display how the historical narrative is influencing what acculturation is approaching, and also that the historical background is influencing the reaction facing the cultural changes.

In Portugal, the word integration means mainly sociocultural adaption. Often, in the Portuguese culture the word integration does not mean that the minority must achieve, at the

same time, cultural adaptation regarding the second cultural, and to maintain its own cultural legacy. In the Berry Model (1997, 2001) learning a second culture does not mean to change the own cultural legacy, but rather to maintain it, which is a contradiction. In Portugal integration can get different meanings, and it is closer to the sociocultural concerns of Durkheim (Safi, 2012). It can take a fusion and an intercultural meaning, because it implies interaction, as on the French approach (Brégent, Mokoukolo, & Pasquier, 2008; Sabatier, & Boutry, 2006). Besides, in the Portuguese cultural background, the minority and the majority are reported as learning with each other, and both cultures are changing.

The religious cultural features can take also an important role, in order to approach the differences between the Portuguese and the Anglo-Saxon cultures. The notion of predestination from the protestant cultures (Weber, 2001) implies a different approach regarding the “stranger” cultures. Thus, the WASP culture does not imply a universalistic point of view regarding the foreigner cultures (Todd, 1994). Detocqueville description of the North American culture was restricted to Protestants and to white persons. Later, Myrdal (1944) described it as the American dilemma. Yet, on the Portuguese Catholic background the universalistic point of view is supporting to mix cultures, and mainly to report the cultural influences from the “stranger” cultures. The Catholic universalistic point of view means that everybody can reach the salvation, not taking into account race and culture. The word Catholic means in Old Greek universal. According to Leung and Van de Vijver (1997): “. . . A study of construct bias will require the collection of additional data to investigate the applicability of the construct and instrument.” (Leung, & Van de Vijver, 1997, p. 13). The Historical data fits on this last goal.

4.4 Sources of data

The current content analysis is applying the Rudmin model in two Portuguese historical books. *The travels of Mendes Pinto* (Catz, 1989; Pinto, 1974, 1989a, 1989b) and the *Historia do Japam* of Luís de Fróis. These books are the best sources, in order to report acculturation as interactive, and as a learning and motivated phenomenon. In the books, there

are two-ways of cultural contributions, because the Europeans are also learning a second culture.

The Western relationship with Japan was inaugurated by Portugal in 1542 or in 1543 (Lidin, 2002; Newitt, 2005). Japan is a common target for cross-cultural comparisons (Benedict, 1946; Matsumoto, 2006). Japan is well-known as being acculturated and, at the same time, for maintaining its own cultural features. Japan is a case of cultural reaction, and of active reinterpretation (Matsumoto, 2006), often under antagonistic acculturation processes.

During the 16th century, the Portuguese and Japanese meeting was remarkable, because the military power was in the Japanese side (Pina, 2001; Tolosana, 2005). Furthermore, China and Japan were perceived by the “Portuguese people” as alike cultures (Catz, 1981; Lévi-Strauss, 1998). Therefore, in the current article, the intercultural appraisals are offering a lesser ethnocentric point of view. Another advantage is the few preconceptions on both cultures (Nakai, 2003), because it was a fresh intercultural encounter. The acculturation approach entails three prerequisites (Sam, 2006); cultural contact with a different culture, reciprocal cultural influences, and changes at individual and collective levels. Therefore, the intercultural relationship between Japan and Portugal is under those prerequisites.

5. The travels of Mendes Pinto

The travels of Mendes Pinto (Catz, 1989; Pinto, 1974, 1989a, 1989b) was written by Fernão Mendes Pinto. In the Portuguese original version, it is called *Peregrinação* (Pilgrimage). Fernão Mendes Pinto (1509-10?/11-1583) was an adventurer, an explorer, a merchant, a writer, and a religious person. He sailed to India, in 1537, and he returned to Portugal in 1558. He was one of the first Europeans to reach Japan (Catz, 1981). Pilgrimage was written between 1569 and 1578 (Catz, 1989). The book employs autobiographic, historical and fancy sources (Catz, 1978, 1989). In the content analysis of Castro (2014a), the book was divided into two parts, one was called of Tanegashima chapters, and another part was called of Francisco Xavier chapters.

5.1 *Historia do Japam* of the Jesuit Priest Luís de Fróis

Luís de Fróis (1532-1597) was born in Lisbon. In 1563, he arrives in Japan. In Hirado, he learnt the Japanese language, and he preached the Catholic Faith. Between 1565 and 1576, he lived in Kyoto. He and the Father Vilela (1526-1572) established close relationship with the main Japanese noble (Shogun Oda Nobunaga), adapting the local customs. Besides, the *Historia do Japam* (1976, 1981, 1982, 1983, 1984), the Fróis legacy is composed by letters, by a book about a Christian Japanese embassy sent to Rome (Fróis, 1993b), and by a book, in which he is stressing a comparison between the European and the Japanese cultures (Fróis, 2001, 1993a; Lévi-Strauss, 1998).

The *Historia of Japam* was demanded by Alessandro Valignano in 1583. Fróis started to write the manuscript in 1585, and he ended it in 1594. However, according to Valignano, the manuscript was too long, in order to acquire social support from Europe, and to work as a handbook for the Jesuits: “. . . I will write in detail about the things that they have written in their books . . . I decided . . . to go where the King is, and afterwards to experience what there exists. I will write in detail to India (Goa), and to the Universities of Coimbra and Rome . . .” (Fróis, 1976, pp. 19-20). The huge *Historia of Japam* manuscript was just published in the year of 1926 in Germany. A second publication took place in Japan in 1938. The Portuguese publication just took place in 1976. Quotes were translated by the current researcher from the Portuguese language to English. The English version of Catz (1989) was not available. The same must be said about the work of Luís de Fróis.

6. Fernão Mendes Pinto and Luís de Fróis in the Rudmin Model

Figure number one, The Rudmin Model. Source: Adapted from Rudmin (2009)

The Rudmin Model (2009) arises after a robust critic (Rudmin, 2003a, 2003b, 2009) at empirical and theoretical levels, regarding the pervasive acculturation model; the Berry one. Rudmin (2009) emphasized acculturation as a learning phenomenon, even because the word acculturation was coined by Powell (1880) connected with learning a second culture. The Rudmin Model has three steps: acculturative motivations, acculturative learning, and changes in the individuals.

The main acculturation topics (Ward, 2010) are present in the Rudmin Model (2009), because the acculturative motivations are including; cultural attitudes, ethnic identity, and coping (see Figure number one). Rudmin has added the utility decision, because motivations are presumed to play an essential role in the acculturation process. All the items are treated as antecedents or as conditions, because they can influence how a second culture is learned. The acculturative learning step encompasses: getting information, instruction, imitation, and mentoring. Learning a second culture is leading towards changes on the individuals, which is the third step of the Rudmin Model. Finally, the model is controlled by discrimination and by socioeconomic status, because they are not acculturation (learning a second culture) per se.

6.1 The acculturative motivations

6.1.1 The Berry cultural attitudes in the F. M. Pinto book

The first item of the acculturative motivations is placed on the cultural attitudes, which guided the research to the Berry Model. The Berry Model (1997, 2001) is grounded in the choice between two dimensions: cultural maintenance and contact. Afterward, it guided the research towards the Berry Model outcomes: the minority acculturation strategies (see the Figure number two), and to the majority acculturation expectations (see the Figure three). The minority acculturation strategies are only answered by the minority cultural group, and it is about their own cultural adaptation regarding the majority culture. The majority acculturation expectations are answered by the majority cultural group. However, it is about how the majority thinks that the minority must get cultural adaptation, and it is not focusing the appraisals about their own cultural changes.

Dimension 1.
Is it considered to be of value to maintain the cultural identity and characteristics?

	YES	NO
Dimension 2: Is it considered to be of value to maintain relationships with other groups?	YES	ASSIMILATION
	NO	MARGINALIZATION

Figure number two, Minority Acculturation Strategies. Source: Adapted from Berry (1997)

Maintenance of culture and identity
Minority

	Like	Dislike
Majority	Like	Melting pot
	Dislike	Exclusion

Intercultural contact

Figure number three, Majority Acculturation Expectations. Source: Adapted from Berry (2001)

According to the content analysis done by Castro (2014a), the Berry cultural attitudes are not working in the Tanegashima intercultural encounter, because no cultural intention and

no previous choice were reported. It was a fortuitous encounter, because the three Portuguese sailors arrived in Japan after a storm. In the F. M Pinto book, it was just possible to find out to be open regarding the intercultural relationship on both cultures. However, no concern about the cultural maintenance was reported. Hence, the book is just fulfilling one Berry Model dimension from the minority acculturation strategies (see Figure number two).

6.1.2 The cultural attitudes on the Luís de Fróis book

In the intercultural relationship described by Luís de Fróis (*Historia do Japam*), the Portuguese minority did not prefer the integration attitude (see Figure number two), but rather they tried to change the Japanese culture. However, the content analysis can be more complex and useful, because the pressure cooker and the melting pot (see Figure number three) are both visible on the intercultural relationship. The pressure cooker can be the correct word if the analysis is focusing the Jesuit Francisco Cabral (1529-1609). He wanted to change the Japanese culture, lingering the European one untouched: “. . . they must be ruled by the European laws and customs . . .” (Fróis, 1982, p. 38). Yet, if the analysis is focusing the Jesuit Alessandro Valignano approach, the acculturation process can be a melting pot: “The Visitor Father had ordered a method by which we must deal with the customs and the ceremonies, and the Japanese manners, which were required by the Japanese.” (Fróis, 1982, p. 177).

Hence, the main difference from the Portuguese historical narrative about acculturation, regarding the pervasive Anglo-Saxon literature, is that a minority (Portuguese and European) tried to change a majority (Japanese), doing cultural adaptation, and mainly that the Portuguese minority was reporting a reciprocal learning process. The Jesuits, as Europeans and as a minority group, were displaying an acculturation pattern with two-ways of cultural influences, in order to achieve their goals:

. . . because the customs of this land and the ceremonies are so different and opposed regarding the European ones . . . that the Father Valignano was ordered that in our houses we should act by the ordinary Japanese way . . . everybody should learn the customs . . . (Fróis, 1982, p. 178)

Another consequence of the Jesuit acculturation process is that it is possible to find out differences inside the same cultural group, even in a very well-organized and motivated social group; the Society of Jesus. The Jesuit learning process regarding the Japanese culture caused divisions among the Catholics, which are well-known as the Chinese Rites Controversy (Minamiki, 1985). Thereby, the generalizations are tough to draw even within the same cultural group, as Matsumoto (2002), and Matsumoto and Yoo (2006) had stressed about the current Japanese culture.

The Japanese were open towards the intercultural relationship, revealing an attitude close to the “integration” option. However, the Japanese clergymen were confronting the European culture. Afterward, the Japanese nobles were expulsing and were chasing the Christians, affecting the Portuguese in a differentiated way: “I determine that the Priests can not stay in the Japanese lands For now on . . . anyone who will arrive from India, and if that person is not disturbing our religious laws, can come freely to Japan.” (Fróis, 1983, p. 406). Therefore, the exclusion attitude can work (see Figure number two) at the same time with “integration”, because the motivations were diverse according to the utility decisions, affecting the Portuguese in a diverse way; according to the different social classes.

The next quote reveals, another time, as the cultural adaptation was complex, negotiated, and mainly that it was multidimensional, because the Japanese wanted the Jesuitical cultural adaptation regarding some Japanese cultural features, allowing the Catholic cultural maintenance in other cultural domains: “. . . it would be better that you get accommodation, regarding the Japanese Bonzos (Buddhist Monks) from the other sects, . . . and that you preach your religion as the Japanese Monks are doing” (Fróis, 1983, p. 396). Comparing these outcomes with the pervasive Berry Model, it is necessary to state that the current emphasis on the “integration” attitude does not take into account diversity inside the same cultural group. The cultural attitudes are changing according to the social classes.

6.1.2 The utility decision

Another Rudmin Model (2009) item from the first step is the utility decision. The utility decision works by the decision between the costs and the benefits, in order to establish and to maintain an intercultural relationship. The acculturative motivations were introduced above, relating adventure (intrinsic motivation) with cultural attitudes. In the Tanegashima chapters from the book of Fernão Mendes Pinto, after the first intercultural meeting, the relationship worked under the economic (trading), and under the curiosity motivations. Afterward, the relationship was working mostly by economic motivation, which is an extrinsic motivation. The economic motivation does not need any cultural attitude to start. Therefore, the relationship was driven by the utility decisions in both cultures.

The Japanese people are described by the Portuguese as curious, and as ruled by the rational thought: ". . . This Japanese nation is the more suitable with the rational thought than other gentiles from this part of the world . . ." (Pinto, 1989, p. 232). In the Japanese culture to acquire new information was reported more important than trading: "Tomorrow, come to see me at my house, and bring me a great gift of novelties about that great World . . . I can assure you that from that commodity, I will buy more than any one." (Pinto, 1974, p. 83).

In the Tanegashima chapters from the Fernão Mendes Pinto book, it was possible to find out an evolution in the relationship. It was also possible to find out different cultural attitudes, and that the motivations were triggered by the utility decisions on both cultural groups. The predominant motivations are curiosity (which is intrinsic), and economic (extrinsic motivation). However, the complexity boosted when the content analysis included the Francisco Xavier chapters. After the first intercultural encounter, the Portuguese tried to establish commercial relationships with Japan, and following the traders were the Jesuits, who were backed by the Portuguese Patronage (Lach, & Kley, 1998). In the Francisco Xavier chapters, the Japanese people displayed a multicultural attitude (majority expectation, see Figure number three), because the Japanese noble gave permission to establish commercial relationships and to spread the Catholic faith.

The Portuguese were taking an assimilation attitude (minority strategy). It reveals a new formulation, regarding the pervasive acculturation literature, because the Portuguese were a

minority without military supremacy. Yet, the Portuguese as a minority were trying to change the Japanese majority. The Japanese “multicultural” attitude did not have the Portuguese concordance (Bourhis, & Dayan 2004; Montreuil, Bourhis, & Vanbeselaere, 2004), because the Portuguese were preferring to change the Japanese culture. The Portuguese behavior is displaying a gap in the Berry Model; the cultural transmission can flow from more than one direction, and the non-dominant group can prefer other option than the majority expectation; the multicultural “integration”. The Portuguese were learning the Japanese culture, maintaining, at the same time, their culture. However, they were trying to change the Japanese culture. The Berry Model results in sixteen outcomes, and not only in four, as Rudmin (2003a, 2003b) have reported.

Among the Portuguese traders, the previous behavior remained the same, and it did not work under any cultural preference, but because of the utility decisions. Besides the economic motivation, the religious conversion was the main Portuguese intention, which is an extrinsic motivation. In this manner, in the Portuguese and in the Japanese cultures the intercultural relationship, and the cultural attitudes were ruled by utility decisions.

The Japanese Monks were perceiving a threat (Montreuil, et al., 2004) at symbolic and at economic levels: “. . . And all the time that the Father was there, which was almost one year, the King provided for him lots of favours, to which the Bonzos were very scared and bothered.” (Pinto, 1989, p. 199). The Japanese tolerance had economic and political motivations, and the social support provided for the Jesuits can be perceived as an utility decision (Kouamé, 2009): “When Nobunaga arose to power, he favoured the Jesuits in many ways: “. . . because he thought that their influence would be of service to him in his campaign against Buddhism” (Lafcadio, 1892, p. 334). The Jesuits were working as economic mediators (Higashibaba, 2001), which increased the likelihood to obtain social support. The Jesuits were trying to allure the Japanese nobles with commercial benefits, and the Japanese nobles were allowing the Catholic activity: “Giving them hope that the trade ship would enter in their seaport, if they would be ready to our religious law”. (Fróis, 1976, p. 270).

The Japanese openness regarding the intercultural relationship was also connected with the intentions of social dominance at the international scenario, because a Japanese noble demanded social support from the Portuguese navy, in order to conquer the Korean Peninsula, giving back the permission to promote the Catholic Church in Japan: “He does not want more for the Priests (Jesuits) than to negotiate with him two big and well-prepared ships . . . and he will build Churches everywhere . . .” (Fróis, 1983, p. 229).

6.1.3 The ethnic identity

Another item from the first step of the Rudmin Model (2009) is the ethnic identity (Rudmin, 2009). The ethnic identity is a dynamic and a multidimensional construct (Phinney, & Ong, 2007), which refers to one’s identity or sense of self as a member of an ethnic group (Phinney, 2003), and it is an individual construction (Phinney, 2000).

In the Tanegashima chapters from the F. M. Pinto book, it is reported that the intercultural learning can occur without any change in the ethnic identity. The Japanese and the Portuguese were open towards the intercultural contact. However, they did not display any concern about their cultural maintenance. As Hutnik (1991) stated, a person can be highly acculturated, but he or she can not change the ethnic identity. The opposite is established by the assimilation model (Teske, & Nelson, 1974), and even by the multicultural model (Castro, 2014a, 2014b, 2015a; Rudmin, et al., 2015).

To learn another culture can take also the opposite effect as to change the ethnic identity, increasing the perceived cultural differences; some Japanese Monks were learning by arguing with Francisco Xavier, and they were perceiving the Jesuits as rivals. Consequently, to be curious, to get information, and to learn a second culture can work in the opposite way as to change the ethnic identity. The separation cultural attitude started with the Japanese clergymen, who were avoiding the rational disputation with the Jesuits: “On the beginning, sometimes, lots of Bonzos (Buddhist Monks) were gathered. They went there to argue with the Jesuit Father . . . and the Japanese religious laws became weaker.” (Fróis, 1976, p. 73).

Taking into account the religious domain, the Japanese were favoring the separation or even the exclusion attitude, but regarding the Portuguese businessmen: “. . . and regarding the ship, it can go to any port . . . but the priests (Jesuits) he does not want to see them.” (Fróis, 1984, pp. 25-26). Therefore, the acculturation process was dynamic, selective, negotiated, and it is a multidimensional process. Moreover, the cultural maintenance is occurring, at the same time, as the cultural changes. The relativity of the acculturation process (Navas, et al., 2005) was not affecting just one cultural group, but rather both cultural groups. It was affecting both groups differently according to acculturative domains, because the social classes from both cultures were taken different motivations.

6.1.4. Coping

To end the Rudmin Model (2009) first step, the content analysis wanted to check out the emotional reactions in the learning situations, and if the emotional reactions were taking a distress or a eustress sense, taking into account the seven face expressions from Ekman and Friesen (2003); enjoyment, surprise, disgust, fear, sadness, anger, and contempt. In the acculturation topic, the coping approach is often just focusing the distress reaction. In the Tanegashima chapters from the F. M. Pinto book, the emotions did not obtain a distress meaning, but rather a eustress. And it was connected with curiosity. Curiosity improved even the general health condition, because the king of Bungo, who was ill, was reporting to feel better and hungry, when he was asking the Portuguese about the novelties of the World: “. . . And nobody can speak, because I want to be the only one who asks him. I can tell you that I liked to talk with him in such way that perhaps I will eat anything later, because now I do not feel any pain . . .” (Pinto, 1974, p. 95). The quote reveals how the motivations can shape the emotional appraisals, and how curiosity is an important way to learn a second culture. In the Tanegashima chapters, surprise is the predominant emotion, which is followed by happiness. The coping topic was not under analysis in the Luís de Fróis book, because most part of the emotions were taking a eustress sense.

6.2 The second step: acculturative learning

The second stage of the Rudmin Model (2009) is the acculturative learning (see Figure number one), which encompasses; getting information, instruction, imitation, and mentoring. Castro (2014a; 2014b) has added the rational disputation or arguing, curiosity, observation, listening, reading, travelling, and the use of internet (Castro, 2015b) as ways to learn a second culture. In the current article mentoring was not approached.

6.2.1 Getting information

During the first meeting described by F. M. Pinto, in Kagoshima a Japanese noble was very curious about the novelties. This situation was reporting getting information and curiosity. To get information was also reported by the King of Bungo, who was the most important noble in the region: ". . . you have in your city three Chenchicogins from the end of the World . . . they are giving you all the information about outside Japan . . . I demand from you to bring me one of the three." (Pinto, 1974, p. 90).

6.2.2 Instruction

In the F. M. Pinto book instruction was also reported, because the noble demanded it from the Portuguese; to teach any medicine to cure the king disease, and to teach how to employ, and to be cunning with the harquebus. Therefore, instruction can include observation by demonstration: ". . . I gave him the harquebus . . . and he demanded from me to teach him how to do gunpowder". (Pinto, 1974, p. 87). Instruction was reported among the Jesuits; to learn the Japanese manners and customs in order to obtain social support, and to convert the Japanese nobles: "The Father gave his graces to the noble . . . in a manner that it is the habit among the Japanese people, as the Brother João Fernandez taught him." (Pinto, 1989, p. 299). Instruction was particularly important in the Luís de Fróis huge manuscript, and it appears connected with imitation and with socialization.

6.2.3 Acculturative learning in the *Historia do Japam* of Luís de Fróis

In the work of Fróis to learn a second culture was intentionally reported as being reciprocal. The ways to learn a second culture were different according to the different cultural attitudes in both cultures. The cultural attitudes were changing according to the different motivations. For example, the “integration” attitude (or just to be open regarding the intercultural contact) displayed by the Portuguese traders was requiring social support, mentoring and getting information. However, the Jesuit’s cultural adaptation, in order to change, and maybe to fuse the European with the Japanese culture, was implying imitation and instruction (socialization).

The Japanese attitude implied to perceive the Catholic Church as alike: “The Bonzo was saying that all the divine attributes that we ascribed to God, Xaca has them as well, and is because of that Deus and Xaca are the same thing.” (Fróis, 1983, p. 351). The word “integration” here means that the Japanese people were open regarding the European culture, encompassing curiosity, getting information and argumentation. Those ways to learn a second culture can be thought as intrinsic motivations: “. . . because of the curiosity some Japanese were asking about the Indian and about the European customs and things, other Japanese were there to listen to the new law and to fight it, other persons were there to mock the Father.” (Fróis, 1976, p. 157).

Sometimes, the ways to learn a second culture were appearing together. For instance, curiosity, getting information, instruction and imitation were appearing, at the same time, in the religious conversion. Firstly, the Japanese were getting information about the European newcomers, and about the Catholic Church, because they were curious. Afterward, they were trying to learn more about the European culture, employing instruction and argumentation with the Jesuits. The behavior triggered by curiosity, by getting information, and by arguing is corresponding to the exploration behavior, in order to devise an ethnic identity (Phinney, & Ong, 2007).

The Jesuits provided importance to instruction, in order to achieve the rational “conversions”, and to get mentoring. The Jesuits were educating the children from the nobles to trigger the imitation behavior in the Japanese people. Moreover, in the schools built by the

Jesuits were living Japanese, Indians, Chinese, and still European students. The mixed culture was taken place also in what the Jesuits were teaching, because the students were learning cultural features from the Asian cultures, at the same time, as from the European cultures. As Fróis wrote:

. . . the youngest ones were learning the Christian language, other were learning to read, and to write our words, and they are able to do it easily in two or three months, other ones were learning the words from Japan and from China . . . they were speaking well the Latin language, which is not so strange for them as we thought before. . . (Fróis, 1982, p. 301).

For the present paper, to instruct children is particularly important, because it was provided an education with reciprocal influences for the Japanese, and for the non-Japanese students, which reports a culture of fusion. According to Simons (1901b), instruction is essential due to learning a second culture, and it is also important to trigger the social influence. Thus, the Jesuit goal was to produce social imitation, in order to build a common ethnic identity grounded in the Catholic culture. The socialization process (instruction) promoted by the Jesuits implied to gather different persons from different cultures, and it implied also to employed different cultural content. For instance, the Jesuits were applying Japanese teachers: “This Brother Vicente was sent by the superior Father to Miaco in order to instruct the youngest from the school about the words and about the sects from Japan”. (Fróis, 1976, p. 173)

The European policies, during the 19th century, were applying the assimilation model in order to standardize the ruling cultures (Bauman, 2004; Hobsbawm, 1990). In the case of the Jesuits, in Japan and during the 16th century, to apply cultural features from both cultures is pointing that the main intention was to fuse cultures (at least, the result was a culture of fusion, which is displayed by the *Kakure Kirishitan*). Moreover, instruction is connected with imitation, because a high social status can render to the social imitation. However, the first effort was triggered by the Jesuits because they needed to learn the Japanese language, in order to be understood, and to argue with the Japanese Monks. Therefore, it was a European

minority that was getting cultural adaptation regarding a non-European culture in order to change it:

Meanwhile, the Visitor Father was given orders . . . because of the great need that there were among the Europeans to learn well the Japanese language, from which our mission is dependent. He orders that all the able persons in the Bungo lands must be gathering in Usuki, and they must get language lessons. (Fróis, 1982, p. 131)

6.3 The discrimination and the socioeconomic status

In the Rudmin Model (2009) the perception about the discrimination and about the socioeconomic status are treated as controlling variables. These variables can influence how a person is learning a second culture. However, they are not acculturation by themselves. In the F. M. Pinto book, the differences in the biological (phonotypical) features are reported. However, those differences were not conveying to any discrimination behavior. Some Japanese nobles preferred the Jesuits, and it caused an antagonistic reaction in the Japanese Monks. Hence, the Japanese Monks were trying to avoid the cultural changes. This situation guided to conflicts among the Japanese nobles, and among the Japanese Monks. Therefore, it guided to a social conflict inside the Japanese society, and in consequence to discriminate the Jesuits.

Regarding the socioeconomic status, on the beginning of the relationship, the relationship was established under costs and benefits. Afterward, the Jesuits were trying to reach the top of the Japanese hierarchy, instructing the sons of the Japanese nobles. Thus, the Jesuits were instructing persons with a high social status, in an attempt to cause social imitation on other Japanese persons:

Because the city of Miaco is the metropolis of all Japan, source of its laws, the main court in which the main noble and the emperor are living. To Miaco is coming people from the 66 kingdoms in a way that what is approved there is praised in the remote lands, and what does not run there anybody pays attention in the other kingdoms. (Fróis, 1976, p. 155)

The Jesuits were trying to get not only social support, but rather to cause cultural imitation, because the social support from a person with a high social status would lead to the social imitation, which was encompassing even the Japanese Shogun: “The favors from Nobunanga and his sons have a great importance. . . And with this situation our law is spreading and is approved by all of them.” (Fróis, 1982, p. 200).

A low social status was not driving to imitation, but rather it was driving even to the social avoidance, not being preferred by the Jesuits, due to the lower power of social influence. Therefore, imitation (Bandura, 2002; Tarde, 1903) reveals the importance of the motivations in the acculturative learning process.

7. Conclusions and suggestions

This paper aimed to report acculturation as a reciprocal learning phenomenon, and still that to learn a second culture was a motivated phenomenon, rather just a matter of cultural attitudes. The outcomes from the intercultural relationship were close to the fusion model, given that there was a new culture emerging, which was corresponding to the H 2.

In the books under analysis, the motivations are shaping the cultural attitudes and the learning process, corresponding to the H 2.1 and to the H 2.2. The second hypothesis was accomplished, because the acculturative motivations are changing according to the different cultural groups (Japanese and Portuguese), and according to their social classes. The motivations are revealing differences in the same cultural group, besides intercultural differences.

In the book of Fróis, it is clearly reported that a minority is learning a second culture, in order to change a majority culture. Therefore, the book is displaying that the pervasive acculturation literature is not fitting in the Portuguese historical background. In the book, the Portuguese minority is learning the majority culture, and the acculturation process is reciprocal,

but it is antagonistic. Taking into account the Interactive Acculturation Model (Bourhis, Moise, Perreault, & Senécal, 1997), there is no concordance between the attitudes from both cultures, which corresponds to the first research hypothesis.

In the relationship between Portugal and Japan, the acculturation process was complex (different strategies were adopted by the same cultural group at the same time). It was also relative, because the same strategies were not always applied, and the same options were not preferred, when the interaction took place in different domains (Navas, et al., 2005). Thus, acculturation was selective in both cultures, and it was multidimensional, and negotiated. Moreover, both cultural groups were affecting each other in a diverse way, according to their social classes. Hence, diverse utility decisions (Rudmin, 2009) were changing the acculturative attitudes.

In the current paper is reported a negative case regarding the pervasive literature, given that the Europeans were a minority. Consequently, the main advantage from the Portuguese historical background is grounded in the fact that a European cultural group is reporting a reciprocal learning process. The Europeans are learning a second culture, reporting it in their own culture. Thus, the Portuguese culture is different, in comparison with the Anglo-Saxon. The Portuguese culture is closer to the fusion model described by Simons (1901a), and by Redfield, Linton and Herskovits (1936), corresponding to the H 1 and to the H 2.

In short, and taking into account the Rudmin Model (2009), the Portuguese and Japanese intercultural encounter displays a two-way process of acculturation under an antagonistic relationship. The relationship is driven by utility decisions, and by strong motivations in both cultural sides. The ways to learn a second culture are all present; getting information, instruction, imitation, mentoring, and they can appear together. Furthermore, curiosity, travelling, arguing, listening, reading and observation are also present. The Berry cultural attitudes are not congruent with both historical narratives. The ethnic identity is revealed as dynamic, complex, multidimensional, and it is not dependent of learning a second culture. Acculturation does not threat the health condition, because most part of the emotions is getting a eustress sense. Therefore, acculturation gains a utility value, given that acculturation

is shaped by motivations. In both cultures is possible to check out different motivations, which are ruling, and are changing the cultural attitudes. Discrimination works under the utility decisions; the Japanese Monks were revealing a clear antagonistic reaction regarding the Jesuits. The socioeconomic status plays an important role under the utility decisions on both cultures. The socioeconomic status is shaping the behavior, and it is providing cultural learning, even because it is connected with the imitation behavior.

The emic effort to contextualize the Portuguese main acculturative characteristics must go ahead taking into account other Lusophone countries. Finally, it is important to state that no model is “better” than other, and that the acculturation process is often antagonistic. In a certain culture, an acculturation model can be pervasive, but some dimensions from other models can work in the same culture. It is stated that the effort to report the European cultures (Geschke, et al., 2010; Rudmin, et al., 2007) learning with other cultures can lead to intercultural tolerance. It is stated that the main Portuguese features concerning the acculturation phenomenon are placed in the fact that it is reported to learn with other cultures, besides the importance ascribed for the interaction (contact), and for the mixture of cultures.

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